

**"CHANGES AND MEASURES TO ELIMINATE CORONAVIRUS
(COVID-19) DETECTED DURING POST-DISEASE REABLITATION
WHEN ACCOMPANIED BY A MALIGNANT DISEASE"**

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Relevance of the topic: the covid-19 (coronavirus disease) pandemic all over the world remains relevant in scientific analysis as a global problem. The specificity of this virus is due to the presence of receptors ACE-2 and CD147, which are located in a wide variety of cells (even stem cells) and tissues, causing the development of many organ lesions[9,10,12].

A new type of coronavirus, SARS-CoV-2 infection (severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus-2) is characterized not only by tropism into lung tissue, but also by a high risk of multiple organ failure [9,12,15].

According to the data presented in the literature, the virus directly affects endothelial cells, calling for endothelial dysfunction, as well as perivascular inflammation, and in some literature, the term "endothelitis" is also used[8,9].

Covid-19 is a severe and complex disease with a heterogeneous phenotype. Coronavirus infection affects the organism of patients in different ways[12]. This infection is very dangerous for patients over 50 years of age, with diabetes mellitus and chronic viral hepatitis. The presence of coronavirus infection with diarrheal syndrome can lead to severe complications of other side diseases in patients and cause death to end[12,13]. It is noted that the consequences of a new coronavirus infection can last for several weeks and months to 1 year after the disease, not only in patients with a more severe course of the disease, but also in patients with a milder form of the disease[14,15,17].

According to foreign researchers, there are residual effects in 20% of cases after coronavirus infection. At least 20 symptom complexes that make up post -

Covid syndrome have been described in the world[16,17,18]. Given the impairment of the functions of many organs and systems during Covid-19, prolonged changes after infection, one of the priorities of the treatment of these patients is complex rehabilitation for the recovery of the body after the disease[18].

Rehabilitation programs are aimed at adapting patients to daily physical activity, maximizing the restoration of lost functions, stabilizing the psycho-emotional state, as well as reducing the risk of diseases of the cardiovascular system, preventing the recurrence of thrombosis and disease[18,19].

Purpose and objectives of the work:

Coronavirus (Covid-19) study of detectable changes and clinical-laboratory characteristics during post-disease reabilitation when accompanied by a malignant disease.

The main task of the work includes:

- Study and prospective assessment of covid-19 in Andijan region cross section with related diseases;
- Study of the peculiarities of Covid-19 and acute diarrhea in patients;
- Study of the specifics of Covid-19 and SVG in patients;
- Study of the specifics of Covid-19 and diabetes in patients.

Тадқиқот
объекти ва предмети:

Objects of research. With the diagnosis of Covid-19, it was observed during the rehabilitation period, having been treated during 2019-2022

There were 96 patients between the ages of 18 and 75.

Subject of research. FVYUKSH was carried out on the basis of the results of the assessment carried out in the diagnostic Department and hospital laboratory, as well as in private diagnostic centers.

Study methodology and methods: when Covid-19 was accompanied by burning diseases, namely chronic viral hepatitis and diabetes mellitus, the clinical features of the disease were studied, and the features of withdrawal of diarrhea syndrome in patients were studied (main group).

The control group was made up of patients who were diagnosed with Covid-19 but had no side diseases.

The study of diarrhea syndrome during rehabilitation was compared on the basis of changes in clinical patterns due to side diseases, transaminases (Alt, ast), total bilirubin content (bound, Unbound), caprogram (microscopy), immune indicators and other clinical signs.

Practical significance of research results

In order to avoid fatal complications, it is recommended to also treat chronic somatic diseases in patients together, start treatment as soon as the diagnosis is made, and continue treatment in an individual way even during the rehabilitation of patients.

Depending on the duration of the disease, we should consider that if the disease lasts up to 4 weeks - acute, if it lasts from 4 weeks to 12 weeks - acute subsection, if it is higher than 12 weeks - postcovidium syndrome i.e. post-covid syndrome. This will in turn be an indication for the patient to determine if the acute period of the disease has passed, but the disease has not fully recovered, and for the continuation of treatment measures during the rehabilitation period.

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